

Part-of-Speech Tagging of Slovenian, 12 years after

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Abstract

The paper begins with a brief overview of the efforts and accomplishments in the field of part-of-speech tagging of Slovenian texts. Quite a few research institutions have participated, and the most prominent Slovenian language technology enterprise. An overview of the POS-tagged 1.3 mil. word text corpus at the Fran Ramovš Institute of the Slovenian Language ZRC SAZU follows. The tags of the machine-tagged texts have been verified by linguists and serve as a resources for the POS-tagging of the 240 mil. *Nova beseda* corpus.

1. Introduction

The term of the paper topic is known in a quite a few incarnations, here they are given by descending order of their quoted Google frequencies (June 18, 2008): *part-of-speech tagging* (207.000), *POS tagging* (107.000), *grammatical tagging* (6.770), *morphosyntactic tagging* (1.880) and *word-class syntactic tagging* (8). It is a procedure during which every word of text is assigned an unambiguous, one-and-only morphosyntactic tag out of a set of all possible tags, associated to a particular word - or wordform, to be more precise. An example is the popular sentence *Danes je lepo vreme* [*Today the weather is fine*], where the following tags could be linked to words: *Danes*{A} *je*{GPce, GOce, Gce, ZOče2} *lepo*{A, Pse1, Pse4, Pže4, Pže6} *vreme*{Sse1, Sse4}. Here the tag values, proposed by the authors in 1996 (Jakopin and Bizjak, 1997, also see http://bos.zrc-sazu.si/cgi/pos_tagging.html) have been used, with the following interpretations: A = adverb, S = noun, G = main verb, GO = the verb to be, GP = auxiliary verb to be in present, ZO = personal pronoun, c = third person, e = singular, ž = female gender, s = neuter gender, 1 = nominative case, 2 = genitive case, 4 = accusative case, 6 = instrumental case. There are $1 \times 5 \times 5 \times 2 = 50$ different ways to associate a single tag to every word and the correct one is *Danes*{A} *je*{GPce} *lepo*{Pse1} *vreme*{Sse1}.

2. Flow of events

Part-of-speech tagging first emerged for the English language in the 1980s; the language is morphologically not so very rich which reflects in a very manageable tagset of around 50 tokens. Languages with higher degree of inflection, such as Slovenian, require much larger tagsets for proper morphological description.

2.1. Early developments

The Slovenian story started in 1996 (Jakopin and Bizjak, 1997) with the development of a stochastic tagger at the Fran Ramovš Institute of the Slovenian Language (ISJ) and a tagset of around 5.000 different tokens, and at the Dept. of Knowledge Technologies of the Jozef Stefan Institute in the course of the Multext-East project (Erjavec and Ide, 1998, Džeroski et al., 2000), which aimed at establishing language resource, based on the annotated novel 1984 (0.1 mil. words), by George Orwell, for the 7 languages: Bulgarian, Czech, Estonian, Hungarian, Romanian, Slovenian, and English (around 2.000 different

tags for Slovenian). Later on the third institution joined the effort, namely Centre of Language Technology, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science at the University of Maribor (Verdonik et al., 2002).

The purpose was practical in all cases: to build a tool, useful for research and for monolingual dictionary development, to foster research of language technologies and to build a resource, useful in speech recognition of Slovenian. Levels of tagging accuracy rose from 80-85% to 90-95% in more specific environments. Resources and tools developed during these early POS-tagging efforts were applied in different fields such as enhancement of entropy calculation (Jakopin, 2002), genre classification (Bizjak, 2005), analysis of the 16th century grammar (Bizjak, 2008), streamlining the annotation of the large text corpus FIDA, prepared by a four partner industry-university consortium and in different speech technology projects (Verdonik and Rojc, 2004).

2.2. Nova beseda and FIDA

Two sizeable text corpora of Slovenian, each targeted at a different audience, emerged around 2000, the monitor corpus *Nova beseda* (Jakopin and Michelizza, 2007), currently comprising 242 mil. words, and the reference corpus *FIDA*, 100 mil. words till 2007 and 623 mil. words since 2007, as FIDAplus (Arhar et al., 2007).

2.3. Recent state of affairs

Resources that could be devoted to POS-tagging were however limited and further research concentrated either in targeting specific language fields (Erjavec and Sárosy, 2006), techniques (Erjavec and Džeroski, 2004), tackling related research areas (Džeroski et al., 2006) and evaluating the current state of affairs (Lönneker, 2005). During the application of the Tree-Tagger, developed mainly for German and English and hence for much smaller tagsets, and applied to a 100 mil. word part of text corpus *Nova beseda*, accuracy estimate of 85% could be obtained (Lönneker, 2005, Lönneker and Jakopin, 2004).

During the time from 1996 to 2006 a reasonable collection of texts (1.3 mil. words), discussed in more detail in Chapter 3, has been machine-tagged and verified by linguists at the ISJ.

More recently the FIDAplus corpus has been tagged by Amebis, the leading Slovenian enterprise in the field of written language technology, using an own, rule-based tagger. The accuracy estimate of 85% has been given during the discussion after the presentation of a recent paper (Arhar and Holozan, 2008).

Whether 85% is a good figure or not depends on the intended use: for some applications it is more useful than for the other.

2008 however witnesses a revival in the field of Slovenian POS-tagging. A new project, JOS (*jezikoslovno označevanje slovenskega jezika* or *linguistic annotation of the Slovenian language*, Erjavec and Krek, 2008), though modest in scale, with a new tagset brought the two main tagsets (Multext-East and ISJ) much closer and a JOS-ISJ interface has been developed and tested during the first Slovenian POS-workshop (Jakopin, 2008).

1	<div id="F0000015"/>		
2	<p id="F0000015.13"/>		
3	<s id="F0000015.13.1"/>		
4	Postopanje	postopanje	Sosei
5	pred	pred	Do
6	afganistanskim	afganistanski	Ppnseo
7	veleposlaništvom	veleposlaništvo	Soseo
8	,		
9	širjenje	širjenje	!Sosei
10	govoric	govorica	Sozmr
11	o	o	Dm
12	tem	ta	!Zk-mem
13	,		
14	kdo	kdo	Zv-mei
15	bo	biti	Gp-pte-n
16	med	med	Do
17	prvimi	prvi	!Kbvmmo
18	letel	leteti	Ggnd-em
19	v	v	Dt
20	Afganistan	Afganistan	Slmetn
21	in	in	Vp
22	kakšne	kakšen	Zv-zmi
23	so	biti	Gp-stm-n
24	možnosti	možnost	Sozmi
25	,		
26	da	da	Vd
27	se	se	Zp-----k
28	sploh	sploh	L
29	uvrstiš	uvrstiti	Ggdsde
30	na	na	Dt
31	seznam	seznam	Sometn
32	čakajočih	čakajoč	Ppnmmr
33	,		
34	so	biti	Gp-stm-n
35	postali	postati	Ggdd-mm
36	del	del	!Somei
37	novinarskega	novinarski	Ppnmer
38	vsakdana	vsakdan	Somer
39	.		

Table 1: JOS-tagged sentence in vertical format

In Table 1 an example of a sentence is given, with token numbers, tokens, lemmas and tags. Approximate translation: *Hanging out in front of the Afghan embassy, spreading rumors about who will be among the first to fly to Afghanistan and what are the chances to join the waiting list have all become part of the journalist's everyday life.*

Table 2 shows the same sentence in horizontal format, as is used at the ISJ, and with tags converted to ISJ tagset.

```
* /<div id="F0000015"/>
* /<POS tagged>
  <p><s>Postopanje pred afganistanskim
      Sse1      E6      Pse6
veleposlaništvom, širjenje govoric o
Sse6      Sse4      Šžp2      E5
tem , kdo bo med prvimi letel v
ZKse5      ZVme1      GFPce      E6      ŠVmp6      GLme      E4
Afganistan in kakšne so možnosti, da
IZme4      Vpr      ZVžp1      GPcp      Šžp1      Vpo
se sploh uvrstiš na seznam čakajočih,
Gmp      A      Gbe      E4      Sme4      PČžp2
so postali del novinarskega vsakdana.</s>
GPcp      GLmp      Sme4      Pme2      Sme2
```

Table 2: Sentence from Table 1 in ISJ format

In Table 2 the same sentence, where tags have been converted to the ISJ tagset, is shown.

Some very welcome simplifications for the future tagging, such as in the adjective-verb relation, have been proposed (Krek, 2008).

3. ISJ POS-tagged corpus

In the decade from 1996 to 2006 a selection of texts from the *Nova beseda* text corpus has been tagged using the own stochastic tagger, supplemented by a database of 3 mil. wordforms and their tags, derived from 270.000 open-class lemmas. The lemmas were taken from the two monolingual dictionaries, The Dictionary of Standard Slovenian Language (SSKJ) and The Dictionary of Lesser Used Slovenian Words (BSJ), produced at the ISJ.

The tagged texts were manually checked by two linguists, the second author and by L. Uršič. The tagger has been integrated into a text editor and text with POS-tags was not shown in the more usual vertical format, shown in Table 1, but a line of text, followed by a line of tags, vertically aligned to words (Table 2). This screen arrangement made the task of manual checking considerably easier, as the text contingency, word context, was not lost to the viewer. In short, tagged text in such a layout was more human-readable.

Besides the mentioned database 3 other lists, extracted from the already tagged and checked texts are used in the disambiguation phase. The first is the list of wordforms with tags and frequencies.

```
tak • M,28; ZKme1,199; ZKme4,57; ZK,19
taka • ZKmd1,3; ZKsp1,9; ZKsp4,9; ZKže1,144
takale • ZKže1,5
take • ZKmp4,51; ZKže2,40; ZKžp1,46; ZKžp4,70
takega • ZKme2,40; ZKme4,18; ZKse2,110
takegale • ZKme4,1
takele • ZKmp4,2
takem • ZKme5,29; ZKse5,11
takemle • ZKse5,1
takemu • ZKme3,9; ZKse3,2
taki • ZKmp1,71; ZKžd1,1; ZKže3,4; ZKže5,25
```

Table 3: Part of the wordform-tag-frequency list

Here code M is used for interjection and ZK for demonstrative pronoun; other codes, used in tags are explained in the discussion of the Table 7.

The second list contains word n-grams (n=2-5) with corresponding tag n-grams and frequencies, as shown in Table 4.

modrim in • Pmp3 Vpr,2;Pse6 Vpr
 modrim in bistrim • Pmp3 Vpr Pmp3,2
 modrim in bistrim razodel • Pmp3 Vpr Pmp3 GLme,2
 modrim in bistrim razodel pa • Pmp3 Vpr Pmp3 GLme Vpr,2
 modrim in drugim • Pse6 Vpr ZDse6
 modrim in drugim zelenim • Pse6 Vpr ZDse6 Pse6
 modrim loncem • Pme6 Sme6
 modrim loncem zajel • Pme6 Sme6 GLme
 modrim loncem zajel vodo • Pme6 Sme6 GLme Sže4
 modrim loncem zajel vodo in • Pme6 Sme6 GLme Sže4 Vpr
 modrim lončkom • Pme6 Sme6
 modrim lončkom nato • Pme6 Sme6 A
 modrim lončkom nato šele • Pme6 Sme6 A Č

Table 4: Wordform-tag-frequency n-grams

Vpr Gmp GLme • 786
 Vpr Gmp GLme A • 34
 Vpr Gmp GLme A E3 • 3
 Vpr Gmp GLme A E4 • 5
 Vpr Gmp GLme A E5 • 1
 Vpr Gmp GLme A GNE • 10
 Vpr Gmp GLme A GNme1 • 1
 Vpr Gmp GLme A Pme1 • 1
 Vpr Gmp GLme A Vpo • 1
 Vpr Gmp GLme A Vpr • 2
 Vpr Gmp GLme A ZObe2 • 1
 Vpr Gmp GLme A ZV • 1
 Vpr Gmp GLme E ZV • 2
 Vpr Gmp GLme E2 • 21

Table 5: Tag n-grams with frequencies

	Multext East	JOS	ISJ	freq.	Description
1.	Ccs	Vp	Vpr	61.639	coordinating conjunction
2.	Rgp	Rnn	A	50.520	adverb
3.	Vcip3s-n	Gp-ste-n	GPce	46.225	auxiliary verb to be in present, third person singular: <i>je</i>
4.	Vmps-smp	Ggdd-em	GLme	37.735	verb participle ending in -l, masculine, singular
5.	Spsl	Dm	E5	33.534	preposition requiring locative case
6.	Q	L	Č	33.351	particle
7.	Css	Vd	Vpo	33.211	subordinating conjunction
8.	Px-----y	Zp-----k	Gmp	25.651	separate verbal morpheme: <i>se</i>
9.	Voip3s-n	Ggnste	Gce	24.905	verb, present tense, third person singular
10.	Spsa	Dt	E4	23.065	preposition requiring accusative case
11.	Ncmsn	Somei	Sme1	19.357	noun, masculine gender, singular, nominative
12.	Spsi	Do	E6	17.662	preposition requiring instrumental case
13.	Ncfsa	Sozet	Sže4	16.244	noun, feminine gender, singular, accusative
14.	Ncfsn	Sozei	Sže1	16.065	noun, feminine gender, singular, nominative
15.	Npmsn	Slmei	Ime1	15.003	proper noun, masculine gender, singular, nominative
16.	Spsg	Dr	E2	14.577	preposition requiring genitive case
17.	Ncmsa	Somet	Sme4	13.843	noun, masculine gender, singular, accusative
18.	Vmps-pmp	Ggdd-mm	GLmp	12.737	verb participle ending in -l, masculine, plural
19.	Ncfsg	Sozer	Sže2	12.692	noun, feminine gender, singular, genitive
20.	Vmps-sfp	Ggdd-ez	GLže	11.951	verb participle ending in -l, feminine, singular

Table 7: Top 20 POS-tags with frequencies per million

Tag codes for both tables are again explained on top of the next page.

The fact that open-class words in Slovenian occur in many inflected forms is the main reason for the ample size of the tagset. This is also the culprit for small frequencies and ample size of the tables. Especially Table 4 and Table 5 are not as dense as one would wish – a lot of entries are Hapax legomena.

An overview of the tagged text collection is given in Table 6.

Collected works of Ciril Kosmač	0.40 mil.
Tomo Križnar: O iskanju ljubezni	0.13 mil.
George Orwell: 1984	0.09 mil.
Plato: Republic	0.09 mil.
The Bible - New Testament	0.15 mil.
Gustave Flaubert: Bouvard and Pécuchet	0.09 mil.
DELO newspaper (1997)	0.05 mil.
Monitor computer magazine (2001)	0.07 mil.
DELO newspaper (2004)	0.07 mil.
Marko Uršič: Four Seasons	0.17 mil.
National Assembly session transcripts (2003)	0.05 mil.
Total	1.36 mil.

Table 6: ISJ POS-tagged corpus overview

It is mainly composed of fiction, there are four translations, a philosophical monograph (Four Seasons), a small amount of general newspaper language (DELO), computerese (Monitor) and formal speech (National Assembly session transcripts).

In Table 7 the most frequent POS-tags from this corpus are given, in all three codings, the Multext-East, JOS and the coding developed at the ISJ. The Multext-East coding of POS-tags is English language based, i.e. V = verb, N = noun, P = pronoun, s = singular, p = plural, m = masculine, f = feminine. As the coding scheme had to fulfill all the grammatic criteria of the 7 languages involved, the codes are also relatively long – average length of the top 20 is 5.25. The ISJ coding has been developed with just Slovenian grammar in mind, G = glagol (verb), GP = pomožni glagol biti (verb to be, auxiliary), S = samostalnik (noun), P = pridevnik (adjective), A = prislov (adverb), Č = členek (particle), e = ednina (singular), p = množina (plural), m = moški spol (masculine), ž = ženski spol (feminine).

Resort to English, or better, foreign abbreviations was only used when it was the only possible option. An example is the abbreviation A for adverb, instead of Slovenian P (prislov). A was used because P found a better use for adjective (pridevnik). As no information, pertaining to other languages and grammars, had to be taken into account, tag lengths also tend to be shorter. Average length of the top 20 ISJ tag codes is 3.10, more than two characters less than the value for the Multext-East coding. Shorter tags, especially if they tend to be self-explaining to the native linguist, are also easier to remember and the uneasy task of hand-checking less tedious. JOS tags are somewhere inbetween, with an average length of 4.50, better than 5.25. Many English abbreviations in coding have been substituted by Slovenian equivalents, such as S for noun (samostalnik), G for verb (glagol). Some fear to use Slovenian however remains, Č was not used for particle

(členek) – second letter in the name, L was used instead, ž not for feminine gender (ženski spol), but z – ž without a hacek. Yet, all in all, a considerable step to make the conversion process easier has been made.

It is also worth noting that the top 20 tags add up to 52% of the total, and 2.180 tags actually appeared in the corpus (out of possible 5.000). Growth curve is shown in Figure 1. Top 2 POS-tags combined cover over 10%

Figure 1: Growth curve for the 2.180 different tags with a total frequency of 1.36 million.

of the whole lot, top 8 combined about 33%, 19 over 50%, 100 about 80% and 200 close to 90% of the entire text. Over one half of the tags, 1.320, have a frequency 10 or above.

POS-tags	freq.	examples
IOme1	1843	<i>Bruno. Janez. Angel. Drejc! Stane!</i>
Č	674	<i>Da. Seveda. Vsekakor. Hvala lepa. Hvala.</i>
A	366	<i>Gotovo. Nujno. Dobro. Očitno. Jasno.</i>
M	334	<i>Aha! Amen. Halo! Hm? Mhm.</i>
GPae GLme	243	<i>sem rekel. sem nadaljeval, sem vprašal. sem rekel, sem nadaljeval.</i>
IOme1 IOme1	215	<i>Filotej (Bruno). Elpin (Janez). Matjaž Klančar Saša Vidmajer</i>
ZK GPce	196	<i>Tako je. Tako je, Tako je!</i>
Sme1	178	<i>Pozdrav. Oče! Stric! Mir! Molk.</i>
IOže1	174	<i>Marija. Tilčka! Ana! Božena! Justina!</i>
ZV	146	<i>Kako? Zakaj? Kam? Kdaj? Kje?</i>
Sže1	143	<i>Tišina. Mati! Neumnost! Mama! Pomlad!</i>
KURL	137	<i>www.microsoft.com www.ibm.com www.apple.com www.compaq.com</i>
GVbe	126	<i>Na! Pridi! Nehaj! Počakaj! Govori!</i>
IZže1 Š K Š	120	<i>Avstrija (100 ATS) 1294,8968 Francija (100 FRF) 2700,9905 Hrvaška (100 HRK) 2554,4020</i>
Pže1 Sže1	108	<i>Vremenska napoved. Gadja zalega! Cela mavrica! Kraška burja. Lepa smrt!</i>
GPce GLme IOme1	102	<i>je rekel Glavkon. je odvrnil Glavkon. je vprašal Winston. je odvrnil Adeimant.</i>
ČZ	97	<i>Ne. Ne! Ne, Ne?</i>
IOme1 GPce GLme	94	<i>Jezus je odgovoril: Peter je molčal. Jezus je rekel: Pécuchet je nadaljeval.</i>
KP KP	91	<i>C. R., G. R., M. B., D. G., D. V.</i>
GPce GLme	86	<i>je rekel. je odvrnil. je vprašal. je rekel, je odgovoril.</i>

Table 8: Top 20 sentence types with frequencies and example

In Table 8 top 20 sentence types are shown – the total number of sentences is 102.000. Very simple discourse-type sentences prevail. The majority of the entries in the table are minor clauses, in the role of calls, greetings and

exclamations such as *Drejc!* (nickname), *Oče!* (*Father!*), *Počakaj* (*Wait!*) and sentences with elliptical clauses, that are grammatically incomplete.

POS-tags	freq.	examples
GPae GLme	243	<i>sem rekel. sem nadaljeval, sem vprašal. sem rekel, sem nadaljeval.</i>
ZK GPce	196	<i>Tako je. Tako je, Tako je!</i>
GVbe	126	<i>Na! Pridi! Nehaj! Počakaj! Govori!</i>
GPce GLme IOme1	102	<i>je rekel Glavkon. je odvrnil Glavkon. je vprašal Winston. je odvrnil Adeimant.</i>
IOme1 GPce GLme	94	<i>Jezus je odgovoril: Peter je molčal. Jezus je rekel: Pécuchet je nadaljeval:</i>
GPce GLme	86	<i>je rekel. je odvrnil. je vprašal. je rekel, je odgovoril.</i>
IOme1 Gmp Gce	81	<i>Bruno se nasmehne. Bruno se zasmeye. Bruno se muza. Bruno se smehlja.</i>
Gae	77	<i>Prosim. Razumem. Grem! Poslušam Mislim.</i>
IOme1 Gce	73	<i>Janez bere: Bruno vzdihne. Janez vstane. Najdù beži. Bruno okleva.</i>
GLme GPce	68	<i>Odgovoril je: Rekel je: Govoril je: Prisluhnil je. Dejal je:</i>
GVbp	68	<i>Izvolite. Pijte! Počakajte! Poslušajte! Berite!</i>
GLme ZOcmp3 GPce	54	<i>Rekel jim je: Odgovoril jim je: Dejal jim je: Dovolil jim je. Odvrnil jim je:</i>
GPce GLme Sme1	44	<i>je pribil stric. je prikimal stric. je vprašal Kovač. je vprašal oče.</i>
IOme1 ZOcm3 GPce GLme	40	<i>Jezus mu je rekel: Jezus mu je odgovoril: Jezus mu je odvrnil: Peter mu je rekel:</i>
GPce GLže Sže1	39	<i>je rekla teta. je vprašala mama. je vzkliknila teta. je poskočila teta. je puhnila teta.</i>
IOme1 ZOcmp3 GPce GLme	39	<i>Jezus jim je odgovoril: Jezus jim je rekel: Jezus jim je odvrnil: Pilat jim je rekel:</i>
Gce	38	<i>Bere. Gori! Bode! Pride! Reče.</i>
Sže1 GPce GLže	38	<i>Brzostrelka je zadrdrala. Množica je jeknila. Množica je molčala. Teta je umolknila.</i>
M Č Gmp GPce GLme Sme1	36	<i>Hm, kajpak, se je popraskal kmet. Hm, kajpak, se je oglasil kmet.</i>
ČZ Gae	33	<i>Ne vem. Ne razumem. Ne morem! Ne smem! Ne maram!</i>

Table 9: Top 20 sentences containing at least one verb with frequencies and examples

In Table 9 the most frequent sentences, which contain at least one major clause, are shown. It is easy to notice that most clauses are exclamative, imperative and declarative. Declarative clauses have a very simple choice of Subjects (1st person and 3rd person masculine). The Predicator most often expresses verbal processes, usually in past tense.

Conclusion

POS-tagging of a morphologically-rich language such as Slovenian brings to surface all the issues, coming from the fluidity and fuzziness of a scientific phenomenon called language, obviously not a very suitable arena for the application of “hard-core” techniques and algorithms so successful in areas such as physics, chemistry or engineering. Yet a combined application of knowledge, accumulated in the available POS corpus and the availability of new resources (Žele, 2008), could definitively bring a positive, acceptable outcome within reach.

4. References

Arhar, Š., Holozan, P. 2008. ASES - Lexical Database as the Language Resource for Slovene Language Technology Development. *Glasnik ZRS Koper*. 3: 30
 Arhar, Š., Gorjanc, V., Krek, S. 2007. FidaPLUS corpus of Slovenian. The New Generation of the Slovenian Reference Corpus: Its Design and Tools. In

Proceedings of the Corpus Linguistics Conference CL 2007. Birmingham 1/219.
 Bizjak Končar, A. 2008. Dvojina v Dalmatinovem Pentatevhu. Symposium *Slovenski knjižni jezik v 16. stoletju*. Ljubljana: ZRC SAZU. 17-19 April.
 Bizjak, A. 2005. *Pridiga kot žanr*. Ljubljana: Založba ZRC
 Džeroski, S., Erjavec, T., Ledinek, N., Pajas, P., Žabokrtsky, Z., Žele, A. 2006. Towards a Slovene Dependency Treebank. In *Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation*, LREC'06. Paris: ELRA, 1388-1391.
 Džeroski, S., Erjavec, T., Zavrel, J. 2000. Morphosyntactic Tagging of Slovene: Evaluating PoS Taggers and Tagsets. *Second International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation*, LREC'00, Paris: ELRA, 1099-1104.
 Erjavec, T., Ide, N. 1998. The MULTTEXT-East Corpus. *First International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation*, LREC'98, Granada: ELRA, 971-974.
 Erjavec, T., Sárossy, B. 2006. Morphosyntactic Tagging of Slovene Legal Language. *Informatica* 30:483-488.
 Erjavec, T., Džeroski, S. 2004. Machine Learning of Morphosyntactic Structure: Lemmatizing Unknown Slovene Words. *Applied Artificial Intelligence*, 18(1): 17-40.
 Erjavec, T., Krek, S. 2008. The JOS Morphosyntactically Tagged Corpus of Slovene. *Sixth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation*, LREC'08, <http://www.lrec-conf.org/proceedings/lrec2008/>.

- Jakopin, P., Bizjak, A. 1997. O strojno podprtem oblikoslovnem označevanju slovenskega besedila. *Slavistična Revija* 45/3-4:513-532.
- Jakopin, P. 2002. *Entropija v slovenskih leposlovnih besedilih*. Ljubljana: Založba ZRC
- Jakopin, P., Michelizza M. 2007. Besedilni korpus Nova beseda. *Mostovi*, glasilo DZTPS, in print
- Jakopin, P. 2008. Oblikoslovno označevanje besedil. *Workshop*. Ljubljana: ZRC SAZU, 5-6 May.
- Krek, S. 2008. Kratek pregled jezikoslovnih zadreg pri oblikoslovnem označevanju slovenščine. *Posvet o sistemih oblikoslovnega označevanja za slovenščino*. UP Koper. April 4.
- Lönneker, B. 2005. Strojno oblikoslovno označevanje slovenskih besedil: Kako daleč smo. *Slavistična revija* 53/2:193-210.
- Lönneker, B., Jakopin, P. 2004. Checking POSBeseda, a Part-of-Speech tagged Slovenian corpus. *Zbornik 7. mednarodne multikonference Informacijska Družba IS 2004*. vol. B:48-55.
- Verdonik, D., Rojc, M., Kačič Z., Horvat, B. 2002. Zasnova in izgradnja oblikoslovnega in glasoslovnega slovarja za slovenski knjižnji jezik. *Zbornik 6. mednarodne multikonference Informacijska Družba IS 2002*. vol. B, 44-48.
- Verdonik, D., Rojc, M. 2004. Jezikovni viri projekta LC-STAR. *Zbornik 7. mednarodne multikonference Informacijska Družba IS 2002*. vol. B, 43-47.
- Žele, A. 2008. *Vezljivostni slovar*. Ljubljana: Založba ZRC.